

Better metadata increases the visibility of scientific articles

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This article¹ discusses the importance of DOIs and metadata for the visibility of knowledge in global bibliographic databases, synthesises findings from recent studies on Crossref metadata, examines new evidence from Crossref on journals hosted on OJS-based [Journal.fi](#) platform, lists concrete options for journal editors to improving metadata, and concludes why this matters especially for Finnish-language scholarship.

Privilege, inclusion and recognition of diverse knowledge contributions

For centuries, scholarly journals have existed to fulfil a core mission: to ensure the evaluation, publication and dissemination of high-quality research. In the era of print, dissemination and visibility depended on physical circulation and indexing by centralised bibliographies. In today's digital environment, it depends on visibility through structured, machine-readable metadata.

The world's largest commercial publishers built their [global dominance](#) not merely through scale or prestige, but by making their content fully discoverable in exclusive digital infrastructures. Their publications have been privileged by inclusion in [widely used](#) proprietary databases, such as Web of Science and Scopus, which continue to define what outputs are considered in research assessment and funding across institutions and countries. Taşkın et al. (2025) show that 74% of the WoS-indexed journals involve professional commercial publishers. Visibility has become both a competitive advantage and a commercial asset.

With the rise of [inclusive, open, community-governed infrastructures](#), such as Crossref, OpenAlex, OpenAIRE, OpenCitations, and others, a profound shift is underway. This can be transformative for local, national and regional journals — often self-published by thousands of educational institutions and learned societies — which have historically been invisible in the proprietary systems (Kulczycki et al., 2025). Through open metadata, these journals now have a genuine opportunity to enter the global knowledge space on equal technical footing.

But these opportunities come with challenges. Small-scale, scholar-led journals often rely on volunteer labour and limited technical support. Ensuring rich, open metadata (affiliations, ORCIDs, funders, references, licenses) requires time, awareness, new workflows and platform-level support. Yet, for regional and national journals, the provision of complete metadata should be understood as an essential service to authors, employers and funders. It is a prerequisite for visibility, recognition, and equitable inclusion in the global knowledge and research information space.

¹ We gratefully acknowledge the valuable discussions and feedback on earlier versions of this manuscript provided by Xenia van Edig, Jorina Fenner, Mikael Laakso, Antti-Jussi Nygård, Sami Syrjämäki, and Jan Willem Wijnen. It has been published in Finnish [here](#).

DOIs and rich metadata are crucial for visibility and recognition

When journals register DOIs with [Crossref](#), they enter a global research information hub that distributes their publications to a wide range of open infrastructures. Crossref feeds metadata to [OpenAlex](#), [OpenAIRE](#), [OpenCitations](#), [CRIS systems](#), library catalogues, disciplinary repositories, and search engines. These systems rely on machine-readable fields to identify who wrote the work, which institutions they represent, who funded the research, what scholarship it cites, and how it should be reused under open licenses.

High-quality metadata ensures that publications can be indexed efficiently and accurately. It enables authors to be uniquely identified via [ORCID](#), institutions to be credited via affiliations and [ROR IDs](#), and funders to trace the outcomes of their grants. It ensures that cited research becomes part of global citation networks that can be tracked through open research information systems, and improves search and retrieval through the availability of abstracts. Metadata on open licenses ensures that the published work can be shared, reused and text-mined in accordance with the authors' rights.

Yet, as Van Eck & Waltman (2025) show, metadata in Crossref remains incomplete: only 52% of journal articles from 2024 include abstracts, 42% include ORCIDs, 30% include author affiliations, and 25% include funding information. The result is an uneven visibility landscape, where some research, especially from international commercial publishers, flows seamlessly into open infrastructures while other work remains undetectable. For promoting openness and equity in knowledge production, dissemination and recognition, improving metadata is therefore not optional but foundational.

Manuscript submission systems shape what metadata gets deposited in Crossref

The study by De Jonge & Kramer (2025) provides the clearest evidence to date that manuscript submission systems play a major role in determining what metadata ends up in Crossref. Every system, even the strongest, shows wide variation. Publishers using the same platform range from excellent to poor metadata providers. This demonstrates that technology alone does not explain the gaps; awareness, training, priorities, and workflow design are equally decisive. Metadata may fail at multiple points: journals might not collect it during submission, systems may not preserve it through production, plugins may be disabled, or publishers may choose not to share certain fields with Crossref.

The analysis of 153 major publishers by De Jonge & Kramer also shows, however, that there are differences between the submission systems. For example ScholarOne and eJournalPress tend to support more complete metadata deposits, while Open Journal Systems (OJS), the most widely used open-source platform globally (Khanna et al., 2022), lags significantly in several key areas. One of the reasons is that OJS serves a highly diverse landscape of small-scale publishers while its operating system is highly configurable: many journals lack the capacity or awareness to activate the appropriate fields, plugins, or workflows.

The CRAFT-OA investigation by Laakso et al, (2024) into OJS-based platforms, such as [Journal.fi](#), confirms that although OJS is an excellent platform for editorial workflow management, it does not guarantee strong metadata by default. Good metadata requires

active configuration, the installation of plugins, careful workflow planning, and ongoing editorial oversight. These findings are corroborated by analyses focused specifically on OJS, notably the work by Kramer & Neylon (2025), who show that while abstracts and licenses are widely deposited by OJS journals, coverage of ORCIDs, affiliations, references, and funding remains low.

The case of Finnish Journal.fi platform: practical steps for richer metadata

[Crossref data](#) produced by Bianca Kramer specifically on 148 serials hosted on the Finnish [Journal.fi](#) provides a detailed look at Finland's national OJS-based publishing platform. Of these journals, 111 (75%) deposited DOIs with Crossref between 2023 and mid-2025. Among them, metadata coverage varies sharply by type (see Figure 1):

- Almost all journals (98%) deposit abstracts
- A strong majority (76%) deposit ORCIDs
- Most journals (69%) deposit license information
- Only 4% provide funder IDs
- None deposit affiliation metadata
- None deposit reference lists

Figure 1: Distribution of metadata coverage in Crossref by Journal.fi journal, for selected metadata types

The pattern discovered for [Journal.fi](#) journals closely mirrors the global OJS landscape. Where OJS offers simple native fields (abstracts, licensing), journals succeed but fail where additional configuration is required (affiliations, references, funding). In many cases, the

journals likely have the information provided by the authors in the manuscripts, such as affiliations, funding acknowledgements and references, but the information is never transformed into structured metadata and exported to Crossref.

What Journal.fi editors can do now: practical steps for better metadata

Metadata dramatically improves discoverability, attribution, and long-term visibility of the published research, which should be of great interest not only for journals and their editors and publishers but also for authors, their employers and funders. The following checklist includes direct links to instructions and technical documentation from PKP, DIAMAS/EDCH, TSV, and Crossref. These steps can significantly improve the quality of metadata deposited from [Journal.fi](#):

A. ORCIDs

- [TSV guidance](#) (in Finnish) on using ORCID in [Journal.fi](#) service
- Enable & configure the [ORCID Profile Plugin](#)
- Require authenticated ORCID sign-in (OAuth)

B. Affiliations & ROR IDs

- Instruct authors, when adding contributors (authors), to fill in their Name, Email, and crucially, the Affiliation (institution name) in the respective fields
- Edit Contributor Details by clicking Edit for each author to ensure their Name, Email, and Affiliation (institution) are entered
- Enable the [ROR Plugin](#), which enables authors to find and add the organization they are affiliated with from the list of organizations maintained by the Research Organization Registry (ROR). In future releases of OJS, addition of ROR to the article metadata during DOI registration will be an inbuilt feature.

C. Funding Information

- [TSV guidance](#) (in Finnish) on Funder information
- Activate [funding metadata plugin](#)

D. References

- Enable references metadata and choose whether authors and/or editors add them
- Instruct authors to paste their reference list, with each reference on a new line, to References field on the submission form
- Enable and configure the [Crossref Reference Linking Plugin](#), which will automatically find DOIs and link them, even if you don't put DOIs in the text

E. Open Licenses

- [TSV guidance](#) (in Finnish) on copyrights and CC-licenses
- Ensure correct CC licenses are set in [Distribution Settings](#)
- Confirm licenses are included in Crossref deposits.

F. Abstracts

- Instruct authors to always place abstracts in metadata fields (not only in PDFs) during the submission process under the "Title & Abstract" section
- Ensure multilingual support if needed by selecting the language tab

Why this matters especially for Finnish-language scholarship

The consequences of missing metadata are particularly significant for multilingual and national research communities. For decades, Finnish-language scholarship has been almost completely invisible in exclusive commercial databases such as Web of Science and Scopus. As long as interoperability relies on proprietary systems, multilingual research remains structurally underrepresented.

Rich, open metadata, including open citation data, offers a transformative alternative. When journals deposit affiliations, references, ORCIDs, funder IDs and open licenses into Crossref, Finnish-language publications become fully integrated into global open infrastructures such as OpenAlex and OpenAIRE. Their authors and institutions become visible in open impact networks, and their citations begin to count in open citation graphs.

This shift directly supports the goals of the [Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information](#), which calls for open, community-governed infrastructures and fully open metadata, and the [Helsinki Initiative on Multilingualism in Scholarly Communication](#), which advocates equal visibility and recognition for research published in all languages. Inclusion and visibility of outputs in global research information infrastructures is an important step making it possible to recognize diverse contributions irrespective of language, according to the [Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment](#) (CoARA) commitments.

For journals and their editors, producing complete and open metadata is not only a service obligation but a direct investment in the journal's own sustainability and reputation. Rich metadata improves a journal's visibility in discovery systems, increases the likelihood that articles are found, read, and cited, and strengthens the journal's standing in open scholarly infrastructures where inclusion increasingly depends on machine-readable information rather than brand recognition. Complete metadata also makes the journal's contribution and impact to national and international research ecosystems legible and demonstrable.

Most importantly, if potential authors perceive that publishing in scholar-led journals limits the visibility of their work — and fails to properly credit their institutions, funders, or cited scholarship — they may gravitate toward commercial publishers simply because they expect recognition and discoverability to be assured there.

Conclusion: Rich Metadata as a Scholarly Service

The evidence from Crossref studies, the analysis of submission systems, and the new Journal.fi findings all point in the same direction. Rich metadata is not merely a technical nicety or administrative task. It is a scholarly service that journals provide to their authors, their universities, their funders, and their readers. Yet, facilitating rich and complete metadata should ideally be the responsibility of the host platform and a measure of high-quality publishing service provided for the journals.

When metadata is complete and open, journals, editors and authors receive the recognition they deserve, institutions and funders can see and validate the impact of their support, citations are integrated into global knowledge and impact networks, and multilingual scholarship — including Finnish-language research — becomes visible, trackable, and

valued. Improving metadata is an investment not only in journal visibility, but in the future of multilingual scholarly communication itself.

Useful resources

- TSV metadata and OJS instructions (in Finnish): <https://tsv-fi.github.io/avoimen-julkaisemisen-palveluiden-ohjeet/#/>
- PKP's Getting Found, Staying Found: <https://docs.pkp.sfu.ca/getting-found-staying-found/en/>
- PKP documentation hub: <https://docs.pkp.sfu.ca/>
- DIAMAS/EDCH guidance: <https://toolsuite.diamas.org/>

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